

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PROJECT	
Project number:	101151942
Project acronym:	GBM4EPI
Project name:	Development of glioblastoma and blood-tumour barrier models for investigating the combination therapy of anticancer agents and efflux pump inhibitors

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1. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

Yes, I will reuse selected preclinical models from previous works to support this project and consequently I will re-use specific basic research and clinical data associated.

First, I will re-use data from preliminary screening results of efflux pump inhibitors (EPIs) tested on resistant ovarian and glioblastoma (GBM) cancer cell models, which identified active compounds for further evaluation in the models tested in this project. Some of these screening data have remained unpublished and have been stored within my previous work group at Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, University of Chemistry and Technology (UCT) Prague, Czech Republic. Hence, they will be included in the first manuscript of this project. Published findings include studies in *Molecular Cancer Therapeutics* (2018, DOI: 10.1158/1535-7163.MCT-18-0533), *Antioxidants* (2020, DOI: 10.3390/antiox9050455), and *Phytomedicine* (2024, DOI: 10.1016/j.phymed.2024.155460).

I will also reuse methodological approaches developed by my current research group at the Department of Oncology, University of Torino (UniTo), Italy, including those described in *Molecular Pharmaceutics* (2019, DOI: 10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.9b00018) and *Fluids Barriers CNS* (2024, DOI: 10.1186/s12987-024-00590-0).

As far as clinical data are concerned, primary GBM cells previously obtained from patients at the UniTo, under ethical approval (#ORTO11WNST), will be reused in the project. Associated clinical data have been anonymized and securely stored in accordance with GDPR 2016/679. The clinical data available to the research team have been already published in an anonymized form in *Journal of Neuro-Oncology* (2013, DOI: 10.1093/neuonc/not104) and *Molecular Cancer Therapeutics* (2018, DOI: 10.1158/1535-7163.MCT-18-0533).

The re-use of these models and consequently of the associated clinical data is aimed to speed up the realization of the Objective 1-2 of the project.

All reused data have been selected for their quality, relevance, and compliance with ethical and legal standards. No suitable datasets have been excluded without consideration.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

The project will generate and reuse data in standard formats. Results of cell viability and spectrophotometric assay of permeability will be saved in Excel (.xlsx) or .csv files and analysed in GraphPad Prism. Transendothelial Electrical Resistance (TEER) measurements, used to assess barrier integrity in the glioblastoma blood-tumour barrier (GBM-BTB) models, will be exported in .xlsx from the measuring device. Quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) data will be generated using Bio-Rad software, stored separately in the original software format and also exported as .xlsx or .csv files.

Western blot images will be captured using a Bio-Rad ChemiDoc Imager and processed with ImageJ software. These files will be saved in .jpeg, .png, or .tif formats. Images from confocal or fluorescent microscope will also be analysed with ImageJ and saved in .tif or .png formats. Figures will be created using BioRender, and graphs will be prepared in Excel or GraphPad Prism, stored as .pdf, .svg, or image files. Reused data from previous experiments including published and unpublished results will be available in Excel, Word, or PDF formats. The anonymized patient data from GBM models will be stored in .csv or .tsv format on secure servers of the host institution in line with GDPR 2016/679. If transcriptomic data is generated, standard formats such as .fastq, .bam, or .csv will be used.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The purpose of generating and re-using data in this project is to support the development, testing, and validation of advanced 5D (five-dimensional) GBM-BTB models. These models will help us to better understand how GBM cells with different degree of differentiation and non-transformed cells from GBM microenvironment interact with the BTB and affect drug delivery and GBM drug resistance.

The data re-used from earlier screenings will help us select the most promising compounds to prioritize in testing on the 5D models that are extremely complex and sophisticated to realize. At the beginning of the project, these models will be employed with compounds whose biological effects on GBM are already known. The data re-use help us to prioritize such compounds. After this phase, we will employ new compounds, without the need of re-using existing data. New experimental data, including results from molecular assays, imaging, and TEER measurements, will be used to test drug combinations, study resistance mechanisms, and group patient-derived models based on how they respond to treatments.

All data collected in the project will help us to reach our main goal, *i.e.* support the development of more personalized and effective-testing models for GBM.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The expected size of the data generated and reused during the project is estimated to be between 30 and 70 GB, depending on the number of experimental repetitions and image resolution. If transcriptomic data is produced during the later stages of the project, the total volume may increase to 100–300 GB. All data will be stored in organized project folders on secure institutional servers with monthly backup on external storage units. The expected size of the data re-used is < 1GB.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The re-used data include:

- Experiments performed by me and my collaborators at my previous institution Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, UCT Prague, including both published and unpublished results. These were generated using standard laboratory methods such as cell viability testing, qPCR, Western blotting, and microscope imaging – clinical and molecular annotations, already published, of primary GBM cells, obtained from surgical samples under ethical approval (#ORTO11WNST).

New data will be produced using similar techniques and instruments, including Bio-Rad qPCR systems, Bio-Rad ChemiDoc Imager, and plate readers. New models of primary GBM, also clinically and molecularly annotated, will derive from the Human Cancer Models Initiative (HCMI) of the American Type Cell Collection (ATCC).

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The data may be useful to researchers working on GBM, drug resistance, efflux transporters, and BTB models. It could also benefit preclinical scientists developing advanced *in vitro* models of organotypic cultures including physiological barriers or preclinical pharmacologists, studying drug combinations to overcome oncological drug resistance. If transcriptomic data is generated, it may support biomarker discovery. Additionally, pharmaceutical companies focused on brain tumour therapies and academic groups involved in biomedical training could also find the data valuable.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes, all datasets made publicly available will be deposited in repositories such as Zenodo or IRIS-AperTO

(University of Turin's institutional repository), where they will receive a persistent identifier, typically a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). This will ensure that the data remains permanently accessible and citable. Scientific publications will retain the DOI assigned by the journal publisher. If associated datasets are deposited in Zenodo, they will receive separate DOIs and will be cross-referenced where appropriate.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes, rich metadata will be included with all datasets to support discovery and reuse. Metadata will contain basic information such as the title, authors, date, institution, type of experiment, cell line used, treatment conditions, file format, and version. This information will be included in the repository entry (e.g. Zenodo or IRIS-AperTO) and in an attached README file when applicable.

There is no specific metadata standard for this research area, so general guidelines such as Dublin Core will be followed where possible. For transcriptomic data, if generated, metadata will follow established formats such as MIAME. All metadata will be written in a clear, structured format to make the data understandable to other researchers.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes, relevant search keywords will be included in the metadata when uploading datasets to repositories such as Zenodo or IRIS-AperTO. Keywords will reflect the main topics of the project, such as glioblastoma, blood–tumour barrier, efflux pumps, drug resistance, patient-derived models, and transcriptomics. This will support data discovery and potential reuse by other researchers.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes, the metadata will be structured to allow indexing and harvesting by repositories and data platforms. This will ensure that the datasets can be found, accessed, and re-used by other researchers.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Yes, data will be deposited in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and the University of Turin's IRIS-AperTO institutional repository. These platforms ensure long-term preservation, open access, assignment of persistent identifiers (DOIs), and compliance with FAIR data principles.

In addition, preprints related to the preprint of manuscripts produced in this project may be uploaded to ChemRxiv and archived in IRIS-AperTO to support early dissemination and long-term access.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Yes, appropriate arrangements have been considered. Zenodo is an open-access repository supported by the European Commission and available to all researchers, including Horizon Europe and MSCA projects. IRIS-AperTO is the institutional repository of the University of Turin and is available for data deposition by affiliated researchers. Both repositories support FAIR principles and assign persistent identifiers.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes, both Zenodo and IRIS-AperTO assign persistent identifiers (typically DOIs) to deposited items. These identifiers resolve to landing pages that include the dataset and its metadata, making the data findable, citable, and accessible to other users.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant

Agreement.

Most of the data produced in this project will be made openly available through repositories such as Zenodo and IRIS-AperTO. However, some datasets will be shared under restricted access for legal or ethical reasons. Specifically, patient-derived data will be handled in compliance with GDPR 2016/679 and the ethical approval granted to the Host Institution. These data are anonymized and securely stored on the institutional server, accessible only to authorized personnel. Additionally, if any results have potential for commercial exploitation, appropriate steps will be taken in consultation with the Technology Transfer Office at UniTo to protect intellectual property before publication. Open access will be provided as soon as legal and strategic conditions allow.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

If an embargo is necessary, for example to complete a patent application or finalize a publication, it will be applied for a limited period, typically between 6 and 24 months. The exact duration will depend on the progress of the intellectual property protection process and publication timeline. As soon as the data can be shared without risk to IPR or confidentiality, it will be made openly available. During the embargo, metadata will remain publicly available to ensure visibility and transparency.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Yes, data made openly available will be accessible through free and standardized access protocols. Repositories like Zenodo and IRIS-AperTO provide open access via DOI links and standard file formats (e.g., Excel, JPEG, PDF), with no login or subscription required. This ensures broad and easy access for reuse.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

If access to certain datasets is restricted due to GDPR 2016/679, ethical approvals, or potential IP protection, they will be stored securely on the institutional server at UniTo. During the project, the access will be granted upon formal request and approval by the supervisor, following UniTo's internal data protection procedures. After the project ends, the same process will apply. Even if the data itself is not public, metadata will be published in Zenodo or IRIS-AperTO so others are aware of the dataset and can request access if needed.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

For restricted data, access will only be possible through secure login with personal UniTo credentials. If someone outside the institution wants to access the data, they must make a formal request. The identity and reason for access will be checked by my supervisor before permission is given. Everything will follow UniTo's data protection rules and GDPR 2016/679.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

No formal data access committee is needed. For this project, access to sensitive data is managed by the research group at UniTo. If someone requests access, the supervisor will review the request and decide, following UniTo's internal data protection procedures and GDPR 2016/679.

Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes, metadata will be made openly available in repositories like Zenodo and IRIS-AperTO. It will be licensed under CC0, as required by the Grant Agreement. The metadata will include information such as dataset title, authors, date, experiment type, keywords, and a DOI or contact details, so users can easily find and access the data. This will follow FAIR principles and help ensure reuse by other researchers.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Data deposited in Zenodo and IRIS-AperTO will be available with no set expiration date. If any dataset becomes unavailable in the future due to ethical or legal reasons, the metadata will remain accessible and findable. This ensures that the existence of the data is known and properly documented, in line with FAIR principles.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes, documentation will be provided to explain what software is needed to access or analyse the data. Most data will be in common formats like Excel, JPEG, or PDF that do not require special software. When specific software is needed (e.g. GraphPad Prism, ImageJ, Bio-Rad CFX), we will mention this clearly in the metadata or README file, and include links or references where possible. If suitable open-source tools are available, they will also be suggested.

2.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Data will be stored in standard formats such as .csv, .xlsx, .jpeg, .pdf, and .docx to ensure compatibility with common software and reuse across disciplines. For transcriptomic data, if generated, standards like MIAME or MINSEQE will be followed. Metadata will be created using general guidelines such as Dublin Core, including descriptions of the experiment, variables, conditions, and units. I will follow FAIR principles and community-recommended best practices, including using controlled vocabularies where possible. A README file will be added to each dataset to explain methods and structure. No new ontology or project-specific vocabulary will be created. If any uncommon terms are used, they will be clearly defined in the documentation.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

It is not expected that I will create new ontologies or vocabularies for this project. If it becomes necessary to use uncommon terms or project-specific definitions, I will clearly document them and, if possible, map them to existing standards. Any such materials will be openly shared to allow reuse or extension by others.

Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Yes, the data will include references to earlier experiments and datasets used in this project, such as previously published EPI screening results or reused data from earlier work. These references will be clearly mentioned in the metadata or README files to ensure transparency and traceability.

2.4. Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Each dataset will include a README file that explains the purpose of the experiment, methods used, type of data collected, and how it was analysed. Variable names, units of measurement, and software used (e.g. ImageJ, GraphPad Prism, Bio-Rad systems) will also be indicated. If needed, a codebook will be included for datasets with more complex variables. This documentation will help others understand how the data was generated and make it easier to validate or reuse in future research.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Yes, all shareable data will be made freely available in Zenodo or IRIS-AperTO with a standard license, such as Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0). This allows other researchers to re-use the data, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement. Sensitive data will remain protected, but metadata will still be openly available.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes, the data will be made usable for other researchers, especially after the project ends. Data will be stored in trusted repositories like Zenodo or IRIS-AperTO with open access and proper documentation, so it can be

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

understood and re-used even by people outside the project. Sensitive data will remain protected, but metadata will still be available.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes, the provenance of the data will be clearly documented. For each dataset, I will include information about how the data was generated, which methods or instruments were used, and whether it was newly produced or re-used. This will be described in the metadata and README files, following general standards like FAIR and Dublin Core.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

To ensure data quality, all experiments will be carried out in technical and/or biological replicates, using proper positive and negative controls. Data will be reviewed for accuracy, and results will be normalized when needed (e.g. qPCR to reference genes). Instruments such as the Bio-Rad qPCR system and Chemidoc imaging system will be calibrated and subjected to maintenance checks regularly. Data will be stored in well-organized formats, with clear documentation to support traceability and consistency.

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

In addition to datasets, the project will generate research outputs such as publications, experimental protocols, images, and figures, which will be shared openly when possible. Data management responsibilities will be coordinated within the research group, supported by the supervisor and the data protection and IT services at UniTo. Sensitive data, including patient information, are securely stored on institutional servers in compliance with GDPR 2016/679 regulations. All human samples are anonymized, and ethical approval has been granted (approval number #ORTO11WNST). These measures ensure secure handling, ethical compliance, and long-term data stewardship.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

In addition to data, the project will generate other research outputs such as experimental protocols, workflows, and *in vitro* models (e.g. 5D GBM-BTB models). The procedures for generating these models will be documented and shared through open-access publications and repositories. Results from combination therapy screening may also be of interest to researchers and pharmaceutical partners and will be published or made accessible when appropriate. While certain physical materials (e.g. patient-derived cell lines) cannot be shared due to ethical or legal reasons, their documentation and handling procedures will be described in detail to support reproducibility.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Where applicable, other research outputs will follow the same FAIR principles as data. Protocols and workflows will be documented in detail and made openly available through publications or trusted platforms (e.g. Zenodo, IRIS-AperTO). Diagrams and figures will include metadata and clear descriptions. Results from combination therapies, if not subject to IP protection, will be published with proper referencing to allow re-use. Outputs that cannot be shared directly, such as patient-derived materials, will still be described in a reproducible way. All shared materials will be properly labelled, referenced, and organized to support discovery and reuse by others.

4. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

The main expected costs related to making data and other research outputs FAIR will come from open access publishing. These costs will be covered through the project budget, with support from the host institution or other funding sources. Data storage and sharing through Zenodo and IRIS-AperTO are free of charge. The preparation of metadata, documentation, and data organization will be part of routine research activities, so no significant extra expenses are expected for data management.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Costs related to research data and output management, including open access publishing and documentation, will be covered through the project budget, in accordance with the Grant Agreement. If additional resources are needed (e.g. for publication fees exceeding the available budget), the host institution will provide support or help secure alternative funding.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The data management will be primarily handled by the MSCA fellow, with support from the scientific supervisor and the data protection and IT services of UniTo. The fellow will be responsible for organizing, documenting, and sharing data in accordance with FAIR principles and ethical standards.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Long-term preservation will be ensured by depositing data and research outputs in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and IRIS-AperTO, which offer free, open access and assign persistent identifiers. Data preservation will be granted for 10 years after the project completion. The fellow, together with the supervisor, will decide which data to preserve based on its value. No major costs are expected, and metadata will remain available even if some datasets are restricted or removed.

5. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Sensitive data, including anonymized patient information, will be securely stored on the institutional server of UniTo, protected by access controls and only accessible to authorized personnel. The server infrastructure complies with GDPR 2016/679 and includes regular backups on external storage devices to prevent data loss. Secure protocols will be used for data transfer. The host institution has specific procedures to follow in case of a data breach. The MSCA fellow has been instructed about these procedures by the supervisor. Public datasets will also be archived in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and IRIS-AperTO, which offer long-term preservation, access control options, and regular system backups.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes, the data will be stored in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and IRIS-AperTO, which support long-term preservation, assign persistent identifiers, and comply with data security and FAIR principles. These repositories are widely used in the research community and ensure stable, open access.

6. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Yes, ethical and legal considerations apply due to the use of patient-derived GBM samples and associated clinical data. All samples used in the project were obtained under ethical approval (#ORTO11WNST) at UniTo. Sensitive data are anonymized and stored securely in compliance with GDPR 2016/679. Access to these data is restricted to authorized personnel. As noted in the ethics section of the Description of the Action (DoA), data sharing will follow all applicable legal and ethical guidelines. Sensitive datasets will not be shared publicly, but metadata may be made available to inform potential users.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Yes, informed consent for data use was obtained from patients at the time of sample collection at UniTo. The consent covered research use, including data sharing and long-term preservation in anonymized form. No new questionnaires involving personal data will be used during the project. All procedures comply with GDPR 2016/679 and the ethical approval protocol (#ORTO11WNST).

7. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Yes, the project will follow the data management procedures of the University of Turin, including the use of the institutional repository IRIS-AperTO and internal data protection guidelines in line with GDPR 2016/679. Additionally, the project complies with the Horizon Europe (MSCA) requirements for research data management, including adherence to FAIR principles and open science practices.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	05.05.2021	Initial version (new MFF).
1.1	01.04.2022	Reformatted to align with other deliverables templates.